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Innovative Tools for Cyber-Physical Energy Systems

Cyber-Physical Energy Distribution Systems: Innovative use cases and future perspectives

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Executive Summary

This white paper, developed as part of the InnoCyPES project funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 program, explores the transformation of traditional energy distribution grids into Cyber-Physical Energy Distribution Systems (CyPEDS). This evolution is driven by key forces such as technological advancements, grid decentralization, and decarbonization efforts. The report presents a novel framework that integrates the Smart Grid Architecture Model (SGAM) with advanced data workflows, providing a structured methodology to uncover interdependencies between critical drivers from both academia and industry. This framework is used to extract two innovative use cases, illustrating the significant potential for innovation in the energy distribution sector.

Innovative Use Cases

- **Peer-to-Peer Asset Management:** This use case investigates the potential of decentralized data storage and privacy-preserving analytics to enhance resource allocation and improve regulatory transparency for Distribution System Operators (DSOs). By leveraging distributed data systems, it enables more efficient asset management and operational decisions.
- **Virtualized Hybrid Grid Operation:** This use case demonstrates how real-time data analysis and cyber-physical applications can facilitate the coordinated management of hybrid AC/DC grids. It highlights the potential for better integration of renewable energy sources and improvements in grid stability through advanced digitalization.

Key Objectives

- **Comprehensive Data Management:** The report emphasizes the crucial role of end-to-end data management, from data acquisition to advanced analytics, across the energy system's lifecycle. A robust digital infrastructure is essential for enabling informed decision-making and optimizing system performance in CyPEDS environments.
- **Policy and Business Alignment:** Beyond technological innovation, the paper stresses the need for aligning business models with policy incentives to promote digitalization in the energy sector. A strategic regulatory framework is essential for fostering investment and expediting the deployment of digital technologies, ensuring that innovation and operational efficiency go hand in hand.

The white paper concludes by offering insights into the practical implementation of these innovations, outlining the challenges faced in real-world applications, and discussing the broader implications for the future of energy distribution. These advancements in CyPEDS not only pave the way for more efficient and resilient energy systems but also support long-term goals of sustainability, decentralization, and decarbonization.

Table of Contents

1	Introduction	4
1.1	About the InnoCyPES Project	4
1.2	Scope of the study	4
1.3	Structure and contributions	5
2	Preliminaries	6
2.1	Cyber-Physical Energy Distribution Systems - Background	6
2.2	Cyber-Physical Energy Distribution Systems - Drivers	6
2.2.1	Engineering, Simulation, and Validation of Software-Defined Protection, Automation, and Control in Smart Grids	6
2.2.2	Decentralized Control Strategies for Next-Generation Grids	6
2.2.3	Distributed Data Management and Integration	7
2.2.4	Data Enrichment Methods for Machine Learning Applications	8
2.2.5	Privacy-preserving Data Pattern Identification for Improved Network Observability	9
2.2.6	Condition Monitoring and Predictive Maintenance of Distribution Grid components	9
2.2.7	Policy and Regulatory Frameworks for Cyber-Physical Energy Distribution Systems	10
3	Framework development and application	11
3.1	The SGAM Framework	11
3.2	Data workflow areas	12
3.2.1	Data acquisition and protocols	12
3.2.2	Data accessibility and usability	13
3.2.3	Data analytics	14
3.2.4	Cyber-physical data applications	15
3.2.5	Policy Analysis	15
3.3	Synthesis of SGAM and Data Workflow areas	15
3.4	Framework Application	16
4	Use cases development	18
4.1	Peer-to-Peer Asset Management	18
4.2	Virtualized Hybrid Grid Operation	19
5	Leveraging InnoCyPES research contributions for practical implementation of use cases	21
5.1	Leveraging the Distributed Data Storage for the Reliability Prediction of Medium Voltage Cables	21
5.2	Missing Value Imputation within Reliability Studies of Medium Voltage Cables	23
5.3	Federated Learning Based Reliability Prediction of Medium Voltage Cables for DSOs	24
5.4	Policy Insights for Cyber-Physical Energy Distribution Systems	26
6	Conclusions	29
7	References	29

1 Introduction

1.1 About the InnoCyPES Project

The contemporary energy landscape is witnessing a paradigm shift driven by decarbonization goals. These shifts require innovative approaches to ensure that energy systems are sustainable and reliable. Amidst this transformative scenario, the European Union Horizon2020 project InnoCyPES¹ emerges as a novel initiative, poised at the intersection of technological innovation, business development, and policy formulation within the Cyber-Physical Energy Systems (CyPES) domain. At its core, InnoCyPES confronts the manifold challenges inherent in building a modern CyPES, recognising the role of interdisciplinary collaboration and holistic approaches in addressing these complexities.

Central to this strategy, there are three foundational pillars, each representing a critical aspect of CyPES development:

- **End-to-End Data Handling Workflow:** The significance of data within the context of CyPES cannot be overstated. InnoCyPES recognises the necessity of establishing a seamless end-to-end data handling workflow, encompassing data acquisition, management, analysis, and its application. By ensuring the integrity, accessibility, and usability of data throughout its life-cycle, InnoCyPES seeks to lay the groundwork for informed decision-making and optimised system performance.
- **Data Analytics Across the System Development Life-cycle:** Effective data analytics serve as a cornerstone of CyPES development, facilitating insights-driven decision-making across the entire system development life-cycle. InnoCyPES endeavours to harness the power of advanced analytics techniques to extract actionable intelligence from vast and disparate datasets. By leveraging analytics to inform design, operation, and maintenance strategies, InnoCyPES aims to enhance the efficiency, reliability, and resilience of CyPES.
- **Business Cases and Policies Incentives Digitalization:** Technological innovation alone cannot drive widespread CyPES adoption. In recognition of this reality, InnoCyPES places equal emphasis on developing compelling business cases and policies that incentivise digitalization and foster an enabling environment for transformative change within the energy sector. Through strategic alignment of incentives and regulatory frameworks, InnoCyPES seeks to catalyze investment in CyPES and accelerate the transition towards a sustainable energy future.

InnoCyPES's collaborative approach is critical to realising these objectives, which brings together a diverse array of academic and non-academic partners in a concerted effort to develop a management tool that supports investment and application in CyPES. This collaborative endeavour is further underscored by the training of 15 highly skilled early-stage researchers (s) who are poised to serve as catalysts for innovation and change within the digitalized energy landscape.

1.2 Scope of the study

In this white paper, we comprehensively examine the interconnections between various projects under the purview of InnoCyPES, delineate use cases to exemplify implementation pathways and extract innovative concepts and research ideas to inform future endeavours.

This report specifically highlights some InnoCyPES projects' outputs within the power distribution domain. These projects are strategically aligned at various junctures across the data life cycle, thereby offering a comprehensive exploration of the breadth and depth of activities within this domain.

Through rigorous analysis and scholarly inquiry, we endeavour to contribute to the discourse surrounding CyPES development and advance our collective understanding of the challenges and opportunities inherent in building a modern, digitalized energy system.

¹Innovative Tools for Cyber-Physical Energy Systems, <https://innocypes.eu/>.

Although these considerations may not be exhaustive, they are grounded in the extensive research and key outputs generated within the InnoCyPES project, providing a solid basis for understanding the emerging trends and innovations in the field.

1.3 Structure and contributions

The report is structured as follows, with key contributions highlighted in each section:

- **Section 2** introduces the concept of Cyber-Physical Distribution Systems and identifies the key drivers behind this emerging innovative paradigm.
- **Section 3** presents the analytical framework developed to integrate these key drivers and components into innovative use cases. This framework combines the layers of the Smart Grid Architecture Model (SGAM) with the stages of the data life cycle, including policy analysis. It provides a structured approach to linking drivers and essential modules, facilitating the development of innovative use cases that span the entire data life cycle and multiple SGAM layers.
- **Section 4** showcases the innovative use cases developed through the application of this framework. Two primary use cases are highlighted, demonstrating the potential for innovation and the opportunities enabled by the new paradigm of cyber-physical distribution systems.
- **Section 5** provides an in-depth focus on specific modules developed during the InnoCyPES process, including practical examples of their application, potential benefits, and limitations.
- **Section 6** summarizes the report's key findings and provides concluding remarks.

2 Preliminaries

2.1 Cyber-Physical Energy Distribution Systems - Background

In the rapidly evolving landscape of modern energy infrastructure, the convergence of digital technologies with traditional distribution systems is giving rise to a new paradigm, referred to in this report as Cyber-Physical Energy Distribution Systems (CyPEDS). CyPEDS represent the next step in modern energy management, where digital tools such as sensors, data analytics, and automation are integrated with physical energy networks to create intelligent, responsive, and optimized systems.

At the heart of CyPEDS is the seamless interaction between the physical and digital layers of energy infrastructure. CyPEDS enhance the efficiency and reliability of energy distribution by enabling real-time monitoring, analysis, and control. This convergence allows for improved decision-making, adaptive responses to operational changes, and predictive management of energy flows.

CyPEDS are powered by advanced data analytics, artificial intelligence (AI), and Internet of Things (IoT) technologies, which together enable dynamic control over energy systems. These systems can predict system behaviour, manage demand, and optimize energy flows through real-time data collection from distributed sensors. Furthermore, CyPEDS support the integration of renewable energy sources, electric vehicles, and energy storage systems, fostering a more decentralized, flexible, and sustainable grid.

As the energy sector transitions to CyPEDS, understanding the key principles, challenges, and opportunities associated with this transformative paradigm is critical. This section sets the stage for exploring the technological foundations and practical applications of CyPEDS while assessing their potential to reshape the future of energy distribution.

2.2 Cyber-Physical Energy Distribution Systems - Drivers

2.2.1 Engineering, Simulation, and Validation of Software-Defined Protection, Automation, and Control in Smart Grids

Traditionally, power systems' Protection, Automation, and Control (PACs) have relied on single-function devices with limited communication capabilities, leading to high design, wiring, testing, and documentation costs. Dedicated hardware for various functions in digital substations increased each project's maintenance and training expenses, with high operational costs and complex development cycles. Moreover, deployments and offline hardware in the loop simulations can be a manual and inconsistent process, which can lead to errors if not automatically validated.

To overcome these challenges, a new power system PAC design trend involves separating functionalities and aims to transform traditional power grids into software-defined smart grids. The objective of the ESR2 project is to validate the applicability of virtualization in digital substations following a three-step approach. First, developing a novel engineering tool to facilitate virtual intelligent electronic device IED integration based on model-driven concepts and IEC 61850 engineering. Next, a real-time digital simulator testbed will be implemented to validate and test the configured controllers and their communication requirements. Finally, an interdisciplinary assessment of both the techno-economical and cyber security impacts of virtualization in digital substations is analyzed.

2.2.2 Decentralized Control Strategies for Next-Generation Grids

The distribution grid is rapidly evolving with technological advancements, incorporating innovations such as renewable generators and electric vehicles. This swift modernization introduces grid stability, resilience, and operational safety challenges. In response, there is a need for a comprehensive analysis of the distribution grid, which now includes potential meshed configurations and DC subsections, forming a hybrid system of both AC and DC components. Various converters are used to integrate these DC and AC segments at different points of common coupling.

To address these challenges, it is crucial to develop decentralized control strategies that ensure the interoperability of converters, providing ancillary services to both AC and DC segments to maintain stability, reliability, and safe operation. Initially, this involves exploring diverse control theory methodologies that might lead to the development of decentralized stability certificates, which are essential for facilitating plug-and-play integration into the grid.

We highlight two key enablers for transitioning from today's power system to a modern one: On the one hand, grid forming control plays a crucial role by enabling the integration of renewable energy sources and other distributed generation units while maintaining grid stability and reliability. This control strategy allows inverters to function as voltage sources, providing essential support to manage fluctuations and ensuring a continuous power supply, even in the absence of traditional synchronous generators. Consequently, grid forming control facilitates the seamless incorporation of decentralized energy resources, enhancing the resilience and flexibility of modern distribution grids. On the other hand, as distribution grids constantly evolve with changing loads and generation patterns, estimating an equivalent model from each inverter's perspective is vital. Data-driven system identification becomes a cornerstone tool in this context, enabling the precise tuning of controllers for specific operational purposes and certifying the stability of current controllers. This approach helps improve stability margins within the grid, ensuring robust and reliable performance.

2.2.3 Distributed Data Management and Integration

Data collected in energy systems are rapidly growing in size and shape. Existing solutions do not provide optimal solutions for the growing demands. This is usually looked at in terms of demands in storage, computing resources, latency, and data extraction. This needs mechanisms for data management using a unique combination of cutting-edge technologies. One of the possible combinations to approach this challenge would be integrating distributed system approaches, database management systems, and data querying approaches to benefit from distributed architecture functionalities while also having benefits related to database management systems (DBMS), such as storage and querying techniques. This is vital in a modern data management world due to ever-increasing data management computing resource demands and the demands of the knowledge to be extracted from the data sets. Combining these technologies provides a streamlined and flexible database design depending on choices and approaches to retrieve integrated data from various sources. These approaches would address challenges related to general data (large) management aspects, looking into storage and retrieval methods considering that data could come from heterogeneous sources.

Similarly, storing data on a single stand-alone server would be impractical given the volume of data already collected and the expected future growth. Many organisations already choose to discard data deemed irrelevant. However, for knowledge extraction purposes, this data is essential, as most algorithms used for extracting insights require large datasets. Two primary methods can be employed as an alternative solution, as illustrated in Figure 1 (Peer-to-peer data storage architecture and distributed queries). In this model, a network of peers is established, where each peer independently hosts its data and manages incoming queries. When a query is initiated, it is propagated across the network to maximise the number of peers that can be queried. Using a peer-to-peer (P2P) architecture to store data helps mitigate the storage overhead issues commonly encountered in centralised systems. However, this approach introduces integration challenges similar to those faced in current systems, largely due to varying database architectures and different data formats representing the same domain. To address these challenges, distributed query support is layered on top of the P2P architecture, allowing for the merging of datasets across peers. For effective data merging, the participating datasets must adhere to a unified database architecture, whether relational or a NoSQL model.

Figure 1: Peer reference architecture for data management

2.2.4 Data Enrichment Methods for Machine Learning Applications

On top of the challenges faced with collecting and storing it, energy systems data requires special treatment. This is mainly due to the quality and/or the amount of data collected from various domains, such as smart meters, SCADA systems and failure records. Modelling the insufficient data at hand probabilistically offers a methodology to overcome these challenges using elaborate sampling techniques. The modelling tools for this purpose span a large spectrum from conventional density fitting (kernel density estimation, Gaussian mixture models, etc.) to more exotic neural network-based generative models (variational autoencoders, generative adversarial networks, etc.). This spectrum of tools offers a trade-off between the computational modelling complexity and performance.

One aspect that practitioners have to be aware of while using these modelling tools is the “data-copying” phenomenon. Namely, highly flexible density estimators (or generative models) tend to replicate the dataset that they are trying to model. This is mainly because of the objective function that they try to maximize and the fact that the individual data points have no uncertainty around them. This causes the flexible models to overfit, which is undesired. Conventional “supervised” modelling methods solve this problem using various techniques. Unfortunately, these do not apply to data modelling problems, which is inherently an unsupervised learning methodology. This is because overfitting to an individual data point (data copying) is already a (singular) solution to the optimization problem.

Above being a singular (or degenerate) solution to the modelling task, data copying brings out unwanted consequences in cases where privacy is a concern. For instance, one of the possible use cases of data modelling is sharing synthetic data with third parties when needed. This synthetic data can be created by taking an (effectively infinite) number of samples from the generative model and sending it to a third party. However, in the case of data copying, the third party is provided with a private data point, and it is indeed a privacy breach.

One method to avoid this problem is using the leave-one-out maximum log-likelihood objective proposed in [1]. The authors proposed a kernel density estimation-based modelling methodology with data-copying mitigation guarantees. Since the resulting model is an explicit probability density model, it can be used for various enrichment tasks on top of synthetic data generation, such as missing value imputation and anomaly detection.

Having an adequate probabilistic model, the aforementioned enrichment techniques can be integrated into the bridge between the data management system and the practitioners using such data for data-driven applications. This can create a seamless pipeline from the data acquisition to the application, as will be showcased later in the use cases.

2.2.5 Privacy-preserving Data Pattern Identification for Improved Network Observability

The increasing digitization of smart grids underscores the growing importance of data-driven applications, highlighted by the proliferation of sensors. Data-driven algorithms are required to be trained with adequate and relevant data for the designed problem. However, the required data might not be available or adequate in an entity or data-holder. Data-sharing concerns might arise among different data-holders/owners when other entities require data access due to various factors such as data ownership, competitive market, further business strategies, security and privacy considerations [2]. One notable example of this is smart meters, which play a pivotal role in diverse applications like energy theft detection, load forecasting, and operational planning through the provision of granular consumption data. Yet, the utilization of smart meter data presents challenges, primarily due to its granularity, potentially leading to the identification of individual consumers. The transfer and aggregation of smart meter data are typically governed by stringent data privacy regulations like the GDPR, which mandate specific obligations for handling personal data.

Navigating these complexities requires a comprehensive approach that addresses both the technological advancements and the ethical considerations inherent in data sharing in smart grids. Privacy-preserving data-driven applications can be utilized to ensure privacy protection while extracting the important features from the data that are not directly accessible.

2.2.6 Condition Monitoring and Predictive Maintenance of Distribution Grid components

The growing electrification of sectors like mobility and heating, combined with the rise of decentralized energy production, necessitates a comprehensive modernization of the distribution networks. Consequently, tools are required that can help prioritize, postpone, and justify investments properly. One possibility is given by applications that monitor the conditions of the components or predict future failures. Thereby, data-driven approaches based on machine learning to indicate the reliability of each distribution grid component are promising to provide required insights for decision-making. The health monitoring of key components, such as medium-voltage cables, is essential in ensuring grid reliability. In Denmark, for instance, medium-voltage cables contribute strongly to state-of-the-art reliability indicators, such as the System Average Interruption Duration Index (SAIDI) and the System Average Interruption Frequency Index (SAIFI). In addition, studies indicate an increase in age-related failure rates for paper-insulated lead-covered (PILC) cables, further emphasizing the need for advanced monitoring systems. The workflow to develop such data driven reliability models of medium voltage cables is presented in Figure 2, and involves data preprocessing steps, such as formulation of data requirements [3], data collection [4], data enrichment [5], data management [6] as well as model development and validation. In the following chapter, the work related to the development of data driven reliability applications is referred to as **dataset creation**, to emphasise the strong relevance of high quality data, and as **data driven reliability prediction method**, to link to new efforts in method development and data analytics.

Figure 2: Conceptual Workflow for the development of applications to model the reliability prediction of medium voltage cables

2.2.7 Policy and Regulatory Frameworks for Cyber-Physical Energy Distribution Systems

Policy analysis plays a key role in shaping the trajectory of CyPEDS, influencing the adoption, deployment, and integration of digital technologies within the energy sector. As CyPEDS continue to evolve, the need for robust and adaptive regulatory frameworks becomes increasingly pronounced, ensuring alignment between technological innovations and policy objectives. Policy analysis facilitates the harmonization of diverse interests, balancing economic interests, environmental concerns, and societal objectives. Policy frameworks create a conducive environment for innovation, investment, and market development within the energy distribution sector by delineating rights, responsibilities, and incentives. Moreover, policy analysis enables proactive adaptation to emerging trends and technologies, ensuring regulatory agility in the face of evolving challenges and opportunities.

Within the realm of CyPEDS and policy analysis, the InnoCyPES project explored 3 main areas:

- **Digitalization Barrier Analysis Framework:** This framework provides a structured approach to identify and overcome barriers hindering the adoption of digital technologies within CyPEDS. Policymakers can create regulatory environments conducive to digital innovation and transformation by systematically analysing barriers and proposing targeted solutions.
- **Sustainable Data Analytics Infrastructure:** A robust data analytics infrastructure is essential for harnessing the full potential of CyPEDS. By establishing transparent, interoperable, and sustainable data systems, policymakers can facilitate data-driven decision-making and optimize the performance of energy systems.
- **Regulation-Driven Digitalization Investments Support Tools:** These tools offer decision support mechanisms for policymakers to prioritize and allocate investments in digitalization initiatives within the energy sector. By aligning digitalization efforts with regulatory objectives and market needs, policymakers can maximize the impact of investments and accelerate the transition towards a digitalized energy landscape.

In summary, integrating these themes within CyPEDS and policy analysis is essential for overcoming regulatory challenges, fostering innovation, and ensuring the efficient and sustainable deployment of digital technologies within the energy sector.

3 Framework development and application

In this section, we outline the process of developing the framework proposed in this paper. Subsections 3.1 and 3.2 provide a brief overview of the SGAM and the data workflow areas, the two core elements that were integrated to create our final framework, which is detailed in subsection 3.3. Lastly, subsection 3.4 describes how this framework was applied to categorize the key contributions of the InnoCyPES projects within the distribution domain (detailed in section 2) and how it served as the foundation for developing the innovative use cases presented in the following section 4.

3.1 The SGAM Framework

Several frameworks have been proposed to facilitate application development for smart grids and CyPES [7]. Their SGAM stands out due to its intuitive structure [8]. The main objective of SGAM is to facilitate the interoperable design of smart grid applications in different hierarchical levels of power system management. With this aim, SGAM is structured after the three dimensions: domains, zones and interoperability layers (see Fig. 3).

Recently, several adaptations to the SGAM have been proposed, such as a better representation of digital actors [9]. However, it still holds as a reference architecture. This study focuses purely on the distribution grid domain; thus, the other domains, e.g. generation, transmission, distributed energy resources, and customer premises, are not considered further. Moreover, this work neglects the distinction after zones as the use cases presented follow the current development towards a system of system approach and thus impact all zones holistically. Consequently, strong emphasis is put on the interoperability layers, which are further explained in the following:

- The business layer in the smart grid context reflects the regulatory and economic structures, policies, business models, objectives, and portfolios of the market parties involved. It supports decision-makers in defining new business capabilities, use cases, and processes.
- The function layer outlines the services and use cases provided by smart grid applications from an architectural perspective, independent of specific implementations or involved actors.
- The information layer focuses on the information exchanged between actors, ensuring interoperable communication through shared data models.
- The communication layer addresses the protocols used for exchanging data, focusing on the syntactic understanding of the information.
- Lastly, the component layer describes the physical components within the smart grid, including systems, devices, and equipment, identified in specific domains and zones of the SGAM model [9].

Figure 3: The Smart Grid Architectural Model (SGAM) [8]

3.2 Data workflow areas

This section describes the key stages of the data workflow in cyber-physical distribution systems. As shown in 4, it consists of the stages Data Acquisition and Management, where data is gathered and organized, Data Accessibility, ensuring data is available when needed, Data Analytics, which turns data into useful insights, Data Applications, where insights are applied to improve operations, and Policy Analysis, which uses data to shape decisions and strategies.

Figure 4: Data workflow areas

3.2.1 Data acquisition and protocols

In the context of a data workflow, data acquisition refers to the initial step of gathering raw data from various sources such as instrumentation, sensors, smart meters, etc. This process involves identifying relevant data sources, collecting data in the correct formats (structured or unstructured), and integrating it into a centralized or decentralized local system for further use. The quality of the data is often ensured through preprocessing steps like data cleansing to remove inconsistencies and errors.

In smart grids, data protocols are essential for ensuring reliable communication between the various components involved in power generation, transmission, and distribution. For this integration to work

seamlessly and a proper data acquisition, standardized data communication protocols are needed. These protocols facilitate the exchange of data between devices, such as meters, transformers, circuit breakers, and control systems. Examples of commonly used protocols in smart grids include Modbus, DNP3 (Distributed Network Protocol 3), IEC 61850, and MQTT (Message Queuing Telemetry Transport). These protocols help manage data flow for tasks like remote monitoring, fault detection, and real-time control, ensuring the grid operates efficiently and securely.

In substations, the IEC 61850 standard has become a key protocol for communication between substation equipment. IEC 61850 is a global standard designed specifically for power utility automation and substation control, focusing on interoperability between different devices and manufacturers. Unlike traditional protocols, IEC 61850 enables fast, reliable communication using an object-oriented approach, where information is modeled in a hierarchical structure. This allows for high-speed data transfer and real-time monitoring of substation equipment. It also supports GOOSE (Generic Object-Oriented Substation Event) messaging, which allows for time-critical events, such as protection and control signals, to be communicated with minimal delay. IEC 61850 revolutionizes substations by enabling advanced automation, remote control, and integration with the broader smart grid infrastructure.

Data accessibility, on the other hand, focuses on ensuring that the acquired data is stored securely and made accessible to authorized users. This involves managing where the data is stored (e.g., local, private utility IT or cloud), implementing security measures like encryption and access controls, and setting up policies for data governance. It ensures that data is available when needed while maintaining privacy and security standards. Beyond accessibility, the workflow typically proceeds to stages like data processing, analysis, and reporting, where raw data is transformed into meaningful insights that can drive decision-making and ensure better power system reliability.

3.2.2 Data accessibility and usability

Considering the current and future data trends in energy systems, data management approaches are to deal with three major challenges: (i) collected data is too big and cannot fit into a single machine, (ii) with its size, it can also not fit in the main memory, and (iii) despite the current storage capacities to store them, practically we can not read them because of time required to retrieve the data. Common methods to deal with these challenges include (i) reading part of the data and ignoring the rest, (ii) for the datasets that cannot fit in the main memory, storage disks can be used, or in some cases, part of data that seem to be of less value can be thrown away, lastly (iii) if data cannot be thrown away, then parallel and distributed systems are used to store them in a distributed fashion.

Although these approaches can partly solve the prevailing challenges, the actual value of the generated, collected, and stored data cannot be realised because of the limitations of the state-of-the-art in facilitating data access and usability. One possible way to address this is by using peer-to-peer data management. This approach brings the capabilities of distributed systems to facilitate data communication among distributed data custodians and database management systems to facilitate data querying using traditional query languages.

Peer-to-peer systems have been in practice for a reasonable time to ascertain their maturity. Since its invention, there have been several improvements in its capabilities. Nodes in these systems are treated as peers, escaping from server-client systems, which positions systems at risk. Traditional peer-to-peer systems were meant to support up to tens of nodes, with limited autonomy and join/leave mechanisms. Modern P2P architectures come with three major improvements. The first is massive distribution—current implementations consider thousands of geographically very distributed sites, with possible clusters forming at certain locations. Second, the heterogeneous nature of sites and their autonomy addresses major concerns with previous implementations of distributed databases. The third improvement is the volatility of the system. In modern P2P architectures, peers are often individual machines and usually leave and join the system at will. Considering these specifications, P2P data management is regarded as one of the appropriate choices for managing large-scale data. These specifications can partly address the challenges of centralised data storage. However, data retrieval would still be a concern.

Data stored in a distributed fashion are usually difficult to fetch and merge to imply the same knowledge. It would require one to go through a tedious cleaning process before the data gets ready for use. Modern peer-to-peer systems provide an overlay to facilitate peer lookup and communication. This gives innovative approaches to adding an embedded database engine so that each peer can benefit from the capabilities of a DBMS. To fetch data from such systems, a client must have an ID of only a single machine among connected peers in a network.

Machine learning and artificial intelligence methods are getting more prominent in the energy systems domain. These methods often require large amounts of "healthy" data to give reliable performances and generalize well. However, the data tend to be scarce and/or incomplete in most cases. One example can be given in the case of smart meter data. These data are generally scarce due to privacy reasons and incomplete due to the varying enrollment of customers into the network. Another example can be given in the context of asset management. The assets in the distribution grids, such as cables and transformers, have been started to be monitored and logged in detail over the last couple of decades. Hence, the knowledge that the DSOs can infer from the older installations is very limited, if not none. Data coming from these types of instances can be "enriched" to mitigate the drawbacks of scarcity and incompleteness.

Problems with insufficient data are not unique to the energy systems domain. In the machine learning literature, extensive research is ongoing for data enrichment methodologies to overcome this insufficiency. However, most of them either take the data of interest very general (such as arbitrary vectors) or too specific to the area (such as image processing). Thus, the enrichment of energy systems data requires domain-specific modifications on the baseline methodologies to preserve the usability of the data.

Modelling the datasets at hand probabilistically (either implicitly or explicitly) is one of the promising approaches for data enrichment. This is due to the data sampling capabilities of such models. After the required modifications, this sampling power can be used to generate (synthetic) records to solve the scarcity problem and/or impute the missing values in the records with the most likely value to solve the incompleteness problem.

3.2.3 Data analytics

Once the data has been collected, structured and enriched, the next step is to derive value from it. This occurs during the processing stage of data analytics. Meaningful insights are extracted by summarizing, structuring, and visualizing the data, as well as by applying algorithms to and developing more advanced models from it. Efforts in data analytics can be categorized into descriptive, predictive, or prescriptive analytics. During descriptive data analytics the focus is put on analyzing and visualizing the data to provide decision support. Moreover, the data is summarized, restructured and interpreted to better understand its composition and reveal underlying patterns. Examples for descriptive data analytics methods developed in the context of cyber-physical distribution grids are data dis-aggregation techniques or behavioural modeling of smart meter data as well as data driven system identification. Furthermore, descriptive data analytics in cyber-physical distribution systems also incorporates privacy-preserving techniques, to ensure sensitive information is protected while still enabling valuable insights. Predictive data analytics often involve advanced data analytics techniques, such as machine learning. Thereby, machine learning and statistical models are employed to forecast future conditions. Examples for the data analytics elaborated on in this report are methods for data driven reliability prediction of medium voltage cables or the detection of cyber attacks for distribution system state estimation. Lastly, prescriptive data analytics aims for revealing the action necessary for a particular scenario, based on data. Thereby prescriptive analytics uses both descriptive and predictive analytics but focuses more on actionable insights rather than data monitoring and pattern identification. Due to the strong overlap with cyber physical data application, prescriptive data analytics techniques are further described in the following chapter.

3.2.4 Cyber-physical data applications

Cyber-physical data applications aim to directly influence physical operations, decision-making processes, and system controls. Therefore, they often harness the insights derived from data analytics. By integrating real-time data from physical infrastructure, cyber-physical applications have the potential to enhance the efficiency, reliability, and adaptability of modern distribution networks. One characteristic of cyber-physical applications is that they often span multiple SGAM interoperability layers, from the Component over the communication and information to the function layer. One example for cyber-physical data application is given by **Double grid forming**. In hybrid grids, which combine both AC and DC components interconnected via converters, reliable operation requires the use of grid-forming inverters to maintain stable voltage and frequency. Grid-forming control is necessary on both the AC and DC sides. This approach offers several advantages, such as the ability to regulate voltage levels in both grids, allowing for better control of power flow—a key objective in meshed grid systems.

3.2.5 Policy Analysis

In the data workflow framework context, policy analysis is essential for ensuring that data integration and application within CyPES are effective, compliant, and aligned with regulatory objectives. Additionally, it should establish a supportive framework that encourages investments in innovation for the energy distribution grid. The following outlines the key components of policy analysis within this framework:

- **Integration with data acquisition and management:** policy analysis involves assessing existing regulations and guidelines that govern data collection and management practices. It ensures that data acquisition processes are compliant with legal standards, privacy concerns, and ethical considerations.
- **Influencing data accessibility and usability:** effective policy analysis examines how regulations affect data accessibility for various stakeholders, including utilities, consumers, and researchers. It aims to promote policies that enhance data sharing and usability while protecting sensitive information.
- **Guiding data analytics:** in the analytics phase, policy analysis evaluates how data-driven insights can inform regulatory decisions and compliance measures. It helps identify the implications of analytical outcomes for policy-making and the potential need for new regulations or adjustments to existing frameworks.
- **Supporting Cyber-physical data applications:** as cyber-physical applications rely heavily on data integration, policy analysis ensures that these applications operate within a supportive regulatory environment. It assesses risks, promotes best practices, and fosters innovation while safeguarding public interests.
- **Facilitate economic incentives for digitalization:** develop regulatory frameworks that promote investment in digital technologies to enhance system transparency and interoperability while enabling new business models driven by improved access to and greater granularity of energy data. This approach is important for acknowledging the value of digital investments and ensuring long-term accountability and sustainability.

3.3 Synthesis of SGAM and Data Workflow areas

In this paper, we developed a framework that integrates the SGAM interoperability layers with the data workflow areas described in Sec.3.2, providing a holistic approach to understanding and optimizing CyPES. This framework allows for a structured way to address the complexities of modern energy systems by bridging physical and digital domains.

The SGAM model, commonly used to represent smart grid systems, is organized into five distinct interoperability layers: component, communication, information, function, and business layers. These

represent various aspects of system operation, from physical infrastructure (components) to business processes and regulatory frameworks (business). On the other hand, our data workflow framework encompasses the various stages of data management, including: data acquisition and management, data accessibility and usability, data analytics, cyber-physical data applications, and policy analysis. This framework provides a structured pathway for managing the life cycle of data from its generation to its use in decision-making and policy development. By merging these two frameworks, we created a synthesis that allows for seamless interactions between data processes and the different layers of energy systems, ensuring that key drivers and innovative solutions can be effectively applied across all levels.

This integrated framework provides a comprehensive structure for exploring and developing innovative use cases. It enables the identification of gaps, potential synergies, and opportunities for digitalization, ensuring that all stages of the data life cycle and all SGAM layers are considered in the development and optimization of CyPES.

3.4 Framework Application

The developed framework was applied systematically to structure and integrate the various contributions from the InnoCyPES project. The process involved the following steps:

1. **Mapping contributions to the framework:** The first step involved cataloguing the diverse contributions from the InnoCyPES project. Each contribution was carefully assigned to its appropriate position within the integrated framework, which aligns the SGAM interoperability layers with the data life cycle stages (Fig. 5). This step provided a structured overview, allowing us to clearly visualize how each contribution fit within the broader system, highlighting how the different projects addressed various layers of the smart grid architecture and data life cycle areas such as data acquisition, management, analysis, and policy.

Figure 5: InnoCyPES main contributions mapped within the developed framework

2. **Integration of contributions:** after organizing the contributions, the next step was to establish coherent connections between the various outputs. By identifying synergies across different contributions, we integrated them into a unified structure, ensuring that the connections between outputs formed a cohesive whole. This phase of integration focused on generating case studies that reflected the collaborative efforts across multiple projects, ensuring that they covered as many aspects of the data life cycle and SGAM layers as possible. This approach was designed to highlight innovative approaches and potential applications that emerge when contributions are interconnected rather than treated in isolation.

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- 3. Case studies development:** The outcome of these steps was the development of two comprehensive case studies, each offering an innovative perspective on the future of energy distribution networks. These case studies were designed to encapsulate the integrated outputs of the InnoCyPES project, demonstrating how key innovations in data management, analytics, and cyber-physical applications can transform energy distribution. Both case studies address critical aspects of the data life cycle, such as enhancing data accessibility, integrating renewable energy sources, and improving system interoperability through real-time analytics and advanced communication technologies.

The case studies, discussed in detail in Section 4, serve as practical examples of how the integrated framework can be applied to develop innovative solutions in energy distribution. Following this, Section 5 will delve into some of the interconnections identified through these case studies, providing insights into the broader implications of the InnoCyPES project's research within the energy distribution domain.

4 Use cases development

4.1 Peer-to-Peer Asset Management

Asset Management is one crucial task of DSOs today, e.g., making better investment decisions, adapting operations, or improving resource allocation. However, modern ML approaches in predicting the conditions of the components often face issues regarding data quality, management, and privacy. In particular, for countries where the network is operated by multiple smaller-sized DSOs, different data structures and challenges in terms of data sharing hinder successful implementation. Data enrichment pipelines, P2P storage databases, and privacy-preserving techniques present a promising toolset for overcoming such barriers. Consequently, this use case leverages collected data for reliability modelling, data enrichment techniques, InnoCyPES distributed data storage (IDDS) and privacy-preserving methods to establish a framework that eventually can contribute to a Peer2Peer Asset Management which is illustrated in Fig. 6. Such a framework can also benefit Regulatory Authorities, not only for fostering data harmonisation and increased transparency but also for guiding future pathways for leveraging component risk models to foster digitalisation and modernisation in the distribution grid.

The purpose of this use case is to improve resource allocation by enhancing the prioritization of investments and to increase regulatory effectiveness through the reduction of information asymmetries. The high-level technological requirements include the use of IDDS (Integrated Data Delivery System), data-driven reliability models, privacy-preserving techniques, and a data enrichment toolbox. The key stakeholders involved are DSOs and Regulatory Authorities. The work items from the InnoCyPES project involved in this use case include dataset creation, data enrichment, Peer-to-Peer data storage architecture, distributed queries, data-driven reliability prediction of medium voltage (MV) cables, privacy-preserving data analytics, a risk-based performance framework, and a tool to support regulation-driven digitalization investments.

Figure 6: Peer 2 Peer Asset Management

Implementation is contingent upon the willingness of DSOs, particularly those with high data availability, to cooperate and collaborate with other DSOs. The step-by-step implementation for this use case begins with the creation of a dataset to assess the reliability of distribution grid components. This involves defining the data requirements and collecting and harmonizing data, such as asset, failure, weather, or loading data. The information is exchanged between DSOs, with both the data producers and receivers being DSOs. In the second step, state-of-the-art enrichment techniques are applied to the current data, with each DSO developing its own data enrichment model on its local computing units. The enriched data remains internal to each DSO. The third step focuses on the development of a peer-to-peer (P2P) data storage architecture. This system allows DSOs and external data providers to contribute to a decentralized storage network, with each DSO running on its own computing infrastructure. Next, distributed queries are implemented to facilitate data integration across peer DSOs. This is followed by the development of a machine learning pipeline for predicting the reliability of distribution grid components, with each DSO training the model on its own systems.

Privacy-preserving data analytics techniques are incorporated into the training process to ensure privacy. During this phase, model parameters are exchanged and processed in a higher-level function while preserving the privacy of individual DSOs. Subsequent steps involve adapting the results to enhance existing models used in regulatory frameworks, such as the Common Network Asset Indices Methodology (CNAIM). A risk-based performance framework is defined, with performance outputs leading to model modification proposals. Finally, the process supports regulation development by creating a regulation-driven digitalization investment support tool. This tool produces reports and proposals on incentive schemes, with the information shared between DSOs and regulatory authorities. Cyber-physical application models of the Peer 2 Peer Asset Management are mapped to SGAM layers and data workflow areas as shown in Fig. 7

Figure 7: Central cyber-physical application models of the Peer 2 Peer Asset Management use case - mapped to SGAM Layers and Data workflow

4.2 Virtualized Hybrid Grid Operation

The purpose of this use case is the possible application of the proposed framework in the real-time operation of hybrid AC/DC grids. This use case uses the five different domains of the proposed framework to coordinate and optimize the operation of a Hybrid grid. Hybrid grids have emerged as a promising solution to expand the distribution network, driven by the increasing prevalence of DC loads in modern systems. These grids combine both AC and DC components, connected by interlinking converters that manage the power flow between the two. However, the role of these converters goes beyond simply balancing power; they can also offer ancillary services depending on the specific needs and available resources within the system. This flexibility is particularly valuable in today's landscape, where renewable energy is increasingly significant.

As distribution systems modernize, new actors such as prosumers, aggregators, energy communities, and DSOs are becoming integral to the grid's operation. In this evolving context, operating the grid in a coordinated and flexible manner is crucial, ensuring that every participant maximizes their benefits while maintaining grid stability and resilience, even during sudden changes.

Given the growing complexity and number of devices within the grid, it is essential to implement a virtualized control framework for each Intelligent Electronic Device (IED), shown in the Data acquisition and management domain in Figure 8. This allows dynamic reconfiguration of control parameters based on real-time grid conditions. A virtualized framework enables the collection and enrichment of data, which is critical for grids experiencing frequent fluctuations due to renewable energy sources.

Such data analysis provides two critical insights depicted in the Data Analytics domain in Figure 8. First, it reveals the reliability of primary equipment, allowing us to determine which components can be safely pushed beyond their operational limits during emergencies. Additionally, this helps optimize preventive maintenance, ensuring maximum power delivery capacity and cost-effective investments in equipment upkeep. Second, it allows for modelling the grid's impedance, which is crucial for optimizing grid operation. This model can be derived from measurements at the interlinking converters' point of common coupling, providing a real-time picture of grid behaviour. With this information, we can deliver the necessary ancillary services to balance power flow and ensure efficient supply to all loads.

Once this data is collected and analyzed, it is sent to the domain of cyber-physical data applications. There, IEDs can adjust their control settings to best support the various actors in the system. Moreover, this information helps refine the control strategy for interlinking converters, enabling them to provide grid-forming support for both AC and DC sections, ensuring smooth and reliable system operation.

Finally, successfully implementing a virtualized hybrid AC/DC grid operation requires technical innovation and a supportive, adaptive regulatory framework. For the proposed framework to function effectively, regulatory support must focus on three critical areas: overcoming digitalization barriers, fostering investment in digital infrastructure, and ensuring sustainable data analytics ecosystem development.

The first challenge is addressing the digitalization barriers that hinder the full potential of hybrid grids. These barriers stem from legacy infrastructure, inadequate data-sharing protocols, and fragmented standards, which limit the grid's flexibility and efficiency. A digitalization barrier analysis framework could serve as a vital regulatory tool, systematically identifying and mitigating these obstacles. By doing so, regulatory bodies can remove bottlenecks that impede the seamless integration of digital technologies, ensuring the grid's ability to support real-time operations and dynamic reconfiguration.

Second, it is essential to create regulatory incentives that promote investment in digital technologies, especially those aimed at enhancing grid resilience, transparency, and operational efficiency. This is where regulation-driven digitalization investment support tools come into play. These tools can help ensure that investments are made in key areas such as advanced data acquisition, analytics infrastructure, and IED virtualization, which are essential for real-time grid management. New performance-based incentives, which leverage granular grid data and balanced Capital and Operational expenditure remuneration schemes, can further stimulate innovation. Grants or tax incentives for cutting-edge digital systems can also accelerate their adoption, making the grid more adaptive and resilient to fluctuations, particularly those introduced by renewable energy sources.

The third regulatory priority is establishing a sustainable data analytics infrastructure. Regulations should not only ensure that data is accessible but also make it usable across all grid layers. This will enable real-time decision-making processes, facilitating the monitoring of system reliability and the proactive adjustment of operations as conditions evolve. Additionally, as the volume of energy data grows, sustainable data centres will become indispensable. Regulations must encourage the development of energy-efficient data centres that minimize carbon footprints, ensuring that the digital backbone supporting the grid remains environmentally sustainable. By optimizing both the infrastructure and the operational aspects of data management, these measures will ensure the grid's long-term resilience and capacity to meet future energy demands effectively. Cyber-physical application models of the Virtualized Hybrid Grid Operation are mapped to SGAM layers and data workflow areas as shown in Fig. 8

Figure 8: Central cyber-physical application models of the virtualized hybrid grid operation use case - mapped to the SGAM layers and data workflow

5 Leveraging InnoCyPES research contributions for practical implementation of use cases

This section delves into the specific connections identified within the use cases, grounded in the research and contributions made through the InnoCyPES project. Each subsection will explore key research efforts that address these connections, offering insights into how these developments can enhance the proposed use cases and further advance the integration of digital technologies within energy distribution systems.

5.1 Leveraging the Distributed Data Storage for the Reliability Prediction of Medium Voltage Cables

In this section, we present the core links described in section 4.1, reflecting potential applications in the reliability prediction of MVCs. Core modules in this case, are peer-to-peer data storage architecture and support for distributed queries as presented in Fig. 9

The reliability prediction of medium voltage cables gathers an enormous volume of data from different stakeholders. Thereby, many challenges were observed during data collection, data pre-processing, and sharing. For future developments, data management must thus be properly and proactively handled. In the context of this paper, we refer to the InnoCyPES Data Storage Service (IDSS) – a decentralised data storage service developed in the context of the InnoCyPES project.

The IDSS provides an innovative approach to large-scale distributed data management and integration with the goal that updated data can be managed dynamically and effectively. This offers the opportunity to apply the IDSS to the use case of reliability prediction of medium voltage cables or the asset management of distribution grid operators in general. Involving data from different data owners, industry domains, and data types can provide a promising case study for validating the benefits of IDSS and identifying potential implementation challenges. Simultaneously, the implementation process of the reliability prediction could be highly improved due to the transition towards a fully decentralised, effectively managed database.

One pre-condition for the development of reliability models medium voltage cables, involving data from different stakeholders, is that the data is centrally collected and made available for model training.

Figure 9: A connection of drivers considered in the first use case

In a set-up, where not all data is stored centrally this makes efforts in data collection necessary. Within the ESR 9 InnoCyPES project high efforts of data collection was necessary. One reason was the observed lack of standardization. Not all stakeholders were storing the same features or storing them in the same way. This led to high efforts in data harmonization. Furthermore, it was observed that not all stakeholders follow the same way of sharing the data or are able or willing to share data to the same degree. The formulation of individual data sharing agreements was necessary. Another barrier is represented by the current process of requesting and obtaining data. The data was requested from the stakeholders individually, obtained at different instances in time and in different data formats. Such as set-up implies the risk that the obtained data is outdated relatively fast. Furthermore, the efforts in data collection benefit mainly the current application case. Further use cases or projects face the same problem again, leading to avoidable efforts in data preparation on stakeholder and data collection efforts on central level. Lastly, general challenges in data management became apparent. Due to the central storage of some data (e.g. failure data) and decentral storage of other data (e.g. Asset data), challenges in the combination of the data were observed. However, it should be noted that this is mainly due to missing identifiers or formulated links between the datasets, also represents a problem within the organisations and might only partly solved by an adapted data management structure.

The IDSS brings a combination of innovative approaches to facilitate data management activities. It looks at three main technologies, (i) an implementation of an embedded database system, depending on use cases it could be a relational-based architecture or NoSQL databases; (ii) a data querying interface which provides an interface for clients (peer) to send query statements to the network and (iii) a P2P overlay, which replicates the servers (peers) across an overlay and so enabling the client to get results that comes from all other servers in an overlay. Since the goal of the tool is also to support distributed queries, having a P2P overlay addressed the problem of data integration. To its entirety, this architecture brings a sense of load balancing since there is no single server that is dedicated to storing data that is handled by other peers. The IDSS also enforces a common schema to be shared across peers in a network. This in turn would address the challenges of data redundancy by ensuring that the stored data is complete, accurate and consistent across the network. Like any other distributed system, since no dedicated peer is appointed to provide services to the other, the systems' robustness and availability are improved because the design removes a single point of failure. And since data schema is replicated across the network, it gives the ability to retrieve data from all the peers on a need basis. Support for complex queries is implemented on top of the storage service, ensuring that data integration is achieved. In the current design, the system (based on implemented database architecture)

supports nested queries and basic SQL functions like MIN (), MAX (), SUM () and AVERAGE (), which efficiently retrieve and combine results. With an ability to support by ensuring that quality data is shared with the clients on a need basis. With an IDSS in place, central data management efforts and end requirements would be reduced by facilitating access to existing data storages on the DSO level. This could increase the frequency and speed of central data access. Furthermore, this could lead to more transparent and equal data sharing rules as participation in the IDSS might foster the formulation of standard non-disclosure agreements among DSOs. Flexible access rights to the DSOs involved could still be implemented because the IDSS still allows for keeping certain data tables and features private. Furthermore, the setup ensures freedom to define bilateral peer-to-peer agreements or modifications or specific peer relations. For some DSOs, such agreements are already in place today and could thus be further expanded or modified as required. Even though the IDSS encourages the alignment of features to collect, it still keeps the flexible design choice of tracking external features at the DSO level or attaching them later. For the use case of cable reliability prediction, this represents an important requirement because not all data might be available at the DSO level stage (e.g., Digging activities).

Despite the presented benefits it also needs to be emphasised that the application of the IDSS comes with certain challenges. First of all data preprocessing and harmonisation is a requirement, which pinpoints to the more abstract problem of data standardisation. This implies that the DSOs must agree on a common data structure, data-sharing policy, etc. In practice, both might be hard to achieve. Furthermore, responsibilities for the installation, management and operation of the decentral IDSS need to be defined.

One obstacle to implementing the IDSS for the reliability prediction of medium voltage cables is the lack of a central data structure that could be decentralised. Therefore, before starting with the implementation of the IDSS, the data of the DSOs needs to be harmonised and an aligned data structure is proposed.

5.2 Missing Value Imputation within Reliability Studies of Medium Voltage Cables

This section describes the bridge between data enrichment methods and data-driven reliability prediction of MV cables that appears in the use cases introduced in Section 4.2 and 4.1. This connection is highlighted in Fig. 10.

Figure 10: Visualising the Link between Missing Value Imputation and Reliability Studies of Medium Voltage Cables within the use case of virtualised hybrid grid operation.

Implementing missing value imputation is crucial for the reliability prediction of medium-voltage

cables, given the numerous challenges encountered in distribution grid data analysis. In the context of assessing grid reliability, these challenges include data integrity, scarcity, missing values, class imbalance, and privacy concerns. The issue of missing values is particularly significant because it directly impacts the performance and reliability of predictive models. Machine learning algorithms require complete datasets, and when data is incomplete, it can lead to biased outcomes, reduced model accuracy, and flawed conclusions. Missing values can obscure critical relationships between variables, hindering the ability to accurately predict cable reliability.

Reliability prediction of medium-voltage cables leverages failure data, root data from distribution grid assets, as well as external features (e.g., digging activities). For Denmark failure reasons, types, and dates are well represented. Information regarding cable installation dates and GIS references are incomplete. Also other important datasets, such as the root information of the medium voltage cables, obtains several data limitations, again in particular regarding the installation age of the cable.

Conventional data preprocessing, such as outlier detection, missing value removal, etc. is critical for preparing datasets for machine learning applications. These techniques aim to ensure data quality, consistency, and integrity, laying the foundation for reliable model training and evaluation. However, while traditional data preprocessing is effective, it may not be sufficient in scenarios with data scarcity, class imbalance, or complex data structures. This is where deep generative models (DGMs) come into play. DGMs are neural networks designed to mimic intricate probability distributions, enabling them to generate realistic synthetic data. Within this category, Variational Autoencoders (VAEs) are particularly notable for their unique properties. VAEs are used for data augmentation and missing value imputation by learning the underlying data distribution and generating plausible data points. This process can be especially useful when there are limited samples, allowing models to be trained with a broader dataset without compromising accuracy. Additionally, VAEs offer a flexible and scalable approach that can be adapted to various scenarios with minimal modifications.

When using Variational Autoencoders (VAEs) for missing value imputation in the context of reliability prediction for medium-voltage cables, several challenges need to be considered. These challenges can significantly impact the effectiveness of the imputation process and, consequently, the accuracy of reliability predictions. One of the primary challenges in applying VAEs for missing value imputation in this context is the absence of a reliable ground truth. Ground truth refers to the accurate, validated data that can be used to assess the quality of the imputation. In the context of reliability prediction, where actual failure events or conditions might not be consistently documented, the lack of ground truth makes it difficult to evaluate the effectiveness of the imputation. VAEs are complex deep learning models that require significant computational resources and technical expertise. Moreover, the deep neural network structure of VAEs can make them challenging to interpret. In reliability prediction, understanding the model's internal workings is crucial for validating its predictions. The lack of interpretability can hinder troubleshooting and make it difficult to ensure the model's outputs are reliable. Furthermore, the generated synthetic data must be realistic and maintain the original dataset's statistical properties. Any deviation could lead to inaccurate predictions and impact the reliability of maintenance strategies derived from these predictions.

5.3 Federated Learning Based Reliability Prediction of Medium Voltage Cables for DSOs

The reliability prediction of medium-voltage cables requires the collection of a vast amount of data from different stakeholders. One of the challenges in data collection is the data-sharing concerns of the involved stakeholders. Data owners, mainly DSOs, are not always capable or willing to share their data due to privacy and security concerns or further business interests. Implementing a privacy-preserving and distributed learning method, such as federated learning [10], addresses these concerns as shown in Fig. 11. This allows for the collaborative improvement of reliability models without the sharing of raw data.

By leveraging decentralized datasets, federated learning allows for the aggregation of diverse insights from different DSOs and medium voltage cable networks. Consequently, federated learning can

Figure 11: A connection of drivers considered in the second use case

help improve the performance of the reliability prediction of medium voltage cables without collecting the data in a central manner. This can alleviate the data-sharing concerns of the DSOs and result in a more robust and accurate model. Additionally, federated learning enables continuous model improvement through iterative updates, which can adapt to changing conditions. This not only enhances the security and privacy of sensitive information but also reduces the latency in data processing and decision-making. Ultimately, federated learning offers a scalable solution for enhancing the reliability and efficiency of medium-voltage cable systems, promoting proactive maintenance strategies and reducing downtime.

Although the advantages are evident, it's important to underscore that employing federated learning poses specific challenges. Foremost among these is the necessity for data preprocessing, which underscores the broader issue of data standardization. The federated learning framework requires each stakeholder to prepare a consistent set of features for effective model training. However, DSOs do not store the same features in the same way, which requires an agreement on the way of storing data. This implies that DSOs must reach a consensus on a common data structure. But to reach such a consensus on data storage formats can be challenging and represent a significant barrier for the implementation of a federated learning model design. Additionally, the necessity for a trustworthy central entity to aggregate parameters might present another limitation. This central entity must be capable of securely and accurately merging model updates from various sources, which is crucial for maintaining the integrity and effectiveness of the federated learning process. Lastly, the efficiency of federated learning models is heavily dependent on the processes used to exchange model parameters and other relevant information. Addressing these challenges is crucial for harnessing the full potential of federated learning in improving the reliability and predictive maintenance of medium voltage cable networks.

Implementing a federated learning model for reliability prediction for medium-voltage cable networks involves several steps. First, it is necessary to harmonize the decentralized data across DSOs to ensure consistency in data structure and format. Next, a method for federated learning must be defined, selecting appropriate algorithms that can efficiently learn from distributed datasets without compromising data integrity. Subsequently, a suitable federated learning setup must be developed, which involves choosing the right model architecture and communication protocol to facilitate effective and secure data exchanges. Finally, the performance of the federated model should be compared against traditional centralized models to evaluate improvements in prediction accuracy and operational efficiency. This step is crucial for demonstrating the efficacy of federated learning in enhancing the

reliability and maintenance strategies of medium-voltage cable networks.

5.4 Policy Insights for Cyber-Physical Energy Distribution Systems

The development of CyPEDS, as illustrated through the two case studies in Section 4 of this report, is highly dependent on the establishment of a robust regulatory framework that encourages operators to invest in targeted innovations. These innovations are essential for the realization of CyPEDS, particularly in facilitating advanced network operations. Moreover, the successful implementation of both case studies hinges on comprehensive network digitalization. This digital transformation is vital to establish the necessary infrastructure for collecting, managing, and utilizing network data, which in turn enables a variety of energy network advancements. Without a highly digitalized grid, the technical foundation for these case studies would not exist.

In the context of the InnocyPES project, multiple studies have been conducted to support the development of these use cases:

- A critical **first step** is understanding the complexity of digitalization itself, identifying the obstacles to its implementation, and finding effective strategies to overcome them. To this end, a detailed study was conducted to categorize the barriers faced by DSOs in their digitalization efforts [11]. These barriers, ranging from technical and organizational challenges to regulatory, economic, and behavioral issues, were not only identified but also prioritized according to the DSOs' core functionalities [12]. This prioritization provides valuable insights to both operators and regulatory authorities, helping them target the most significant barriers and accelerate the digital transformation process.

This foundational understanding of digitalization is crucial for the two case studies analyzed in the report. Without a clear analysis of the digitalization barriers and strategies to address them, the investments required to build the necessary digital infrastructure for these use cases would not be feasible. In essence, the pathway to unlocking digital investments is integral to enabling the development and success of these innovative case studies

- **Secondly**, a targeted effort was made to understand how to unlock investments in digital technologies, particularly within the context of energy distribution networks. Economically, such investments remain scarce due to two key reasons: the limited use of comprehensive cost-benefit analyses that fail to quantify and monetize the full spectrum of benefits associated with digitalization, and the absence of effective regulatory mechanisms that incentivize operators to invest in digital infrastructure for network innovation.

As part of the InnocyPES project, a new cost-benefit analysis (CBA) framework was developed [13] and applied in a case study in Portugal [14]. This framework enabled a more accurate assessment of both the costs and the long-term benefits of network digitalization, illustrating how these investments can lead to greater overall efficiency and deliver significant social benefits. Crucially, it highlighted that digital investments, while often overlooked, provide far more sustainable value compared to conventional approaches focused on expanding physical capacity and infrastructure—strategies that tend to be more attractive to investors due to their immediate profitability.

Additionally, a study conducted in Australia examined the interdependencies between regulatory incentive mechanisms and the investment strategies of DSOs [15]. This research provided valuable insights and policy recommendations to enhance regulatory frameworks, aligning them more closely with the needs of digitalization and fostering an environment that encourages investments in digital infrastructure.

Together, the cost-benefit analysis framework and the findings from these studies in Portugal and Australia can significantly support the development of both case studies presented in this report. By offering a clearer understanding of the tangible benefits associated with digital infrastructure

and by improving incentive policies, these studies lay the groundwork for the necessary investments in digital infrastructure, which are essential for the successful implementation of both case studies.

- A **third** critical aspect of the research conducted within the InnoCyPES project was to explore how advanced digitalization in the grid can drive regulatory innovation and enhance the quality and performance of digital infrastructure. A key study focused on better assessing failure risk conditions in energy distribution networks. Specifically, a case study in the UK examined how digitalization could improve data granularity and visibility, and how this could impact the probability of component failure as calculated using the CNAIM methodology [16]. This increased visibility provided more accurate failure risk assessments, offering regulatory authorities a clearer understanding of network operation conditions.

Building on this improved risk calculation, another study was developed to propose a new approach to regulatory frameworks, transitioning from traditional incentive systems—based on performance outputs—to a proactive, risk-based system [17]. This shift encourages DSOs to adopt proactive network management practices, with incentives tied not to past performance but to the management of potential risks. By rewarding or penalizing DSOs based on their ability to mitigate component failure risks, this framework encourages investment in innovation and enhanced network observability, positioning risk management at the core of regulatory oversight.

These two studies—focused on improving failure risk calculation and advocating for a proactive, risk-based incentive framework—are particularly relevant to the development of the first case study related to peer-to-peer asset management. In such a management model, precise failure risk assessments and proactive, cost-effective network management are crucial. Together, these studies offer both a robust framework for risk assessment and a roadmap for regulatory authorities to support better risk-based network management.

- The **fourth** and final research contribution of the InnoCyPES project focused on evaluating the environmental sustainability challenges posed by the high level of digitalization required for CyPEDS implementation. While digitalization offers significant advantages in terms of enhancing energy efficiency and optimizing system operations, it also brings new environmental concerns. These include increased energy consumption from digital technologies, potential rebound effects on consumer behavior, and sustainability issues related to data management, particularly in data centers [18]. Data centers, which play a critical role in supporting advanced analytics, optimization, and automation within the energy sector, are among the largest consumers of energy and resources. This is particularly evident in their significant water usage for cooling and the growing issue of electronic waste from obsolete hardware. To address these challenges, the research developed a comprehensive framework aimed at improving the sustainability of data centers. The framework emphasizes the importance of designing energy-efficient and resource-conscious data centers by establishing key performance indicators (KPIs) that track energy use, water consumption, and electronic waste management. Additionally, the research proposed innovative metrics to assess the efficiency of data utilization, with the goal of reducing unnecessary data storage and processing. By ensuring a more efficient balance between data usage and storage, the energy demand of digital infrastructure can be minimized. The study also explored how data centers could play a role in demand response initiatives, contributing to grid flexibility by dynamically adjusting their energy consumption during peak periods and leveraging local data caching to reduce computational loads.

The findings from this research offer valuable contributions for the two CyPEDS case studies identified. By optimizing the energy consumption and environmental footprint of data centers, the digital infrastructure supporting the two use cases can operate sustainably without adding undue strain on resources. The proposed KPIs and efficiency metrics can ensure that data centers are not only energy-efficient but also capable of adjusting their operations dynamically to support grid

flexibility. Overall, through these contributions, the InnoCyPES project outlines a path for ensuring that the digital transformation in the energy sector not only enhances system performance but also aligns with broader sustainability goals, supporting both decarbonization efforts and energy security.

In summary, the research contributions of the InnoCyPES project provide a comprehensive framework for advancing Cyber-Physical Energy Distribution Systems. By addressing the critical barriers to digitalization, developing robust cost-benefit analysis frameworks, proposing innovative regulatory approaches, and evaluating the environmental implications of digital infrastructure, the project lays an initial foundation for the successful implementation of the CyPES case studies. These insights not only facilitate enhanced energy efficiency and system optimization but also ensure that the transition toward digitalization occurs in a sustainable manner. As the energy sector continues to evolve, the findings from this project serve as essential guidelines for operators and regulators alike, ensuring that both the Peer-to-Peer Asset Management and Virtualized Hybrid Grid Operation models are executed effectively, aligning technological advancement with regulatory innovation and environmental responsibility.

6 Conclusions

This report has presented the development and application of an integrated framework designed to merge the SGAM interoperability layers with the data life cycle framework. By doing so, we structured and connected the diverse contributions from the InnoCyPES project, enabling the identification of innovative use cases that address key challenges in energy distribution systems. This approach not only allowed us to systematically organize and integrate the project outputs, but also facilitated the exploration of new possibilities within the evolving landscape of Cyber-Physical Energy Distribution Systems.

Two primary use cases were developed through this process: **Peer-to-Peer Asset Management** and **Virtualised Hybrid Grid Operation**.

1. Peer-to-Peer Asset Management focuses on decentralized energy resource management at a DSO level, where individual assets—such as renewable energy systems, storage units, and prosumers—can engage in dynamic, real-time interactions. This use case leverages advanced data analytics, management, integration and interoperability to enable participants to optimize their energy consumption, production, and trading directly, fostering a more decentralized and transparent energy market.
2. Virtualised Hybrid Grid Operation explores the integration of physical grid infrastructure with digital twin technology. By creating virtual models of the grid, operators can simulate various scenarios, optimize energy flows, and predict system behaviour. This use case enhances grid flexibility, particularly in integrating renewable energy sources and electric vehicles, ensuring smoother operations in both traditional and decentralized energy systems.

These use cases not only demonstrate the innovative potential of the InnoCyPES project's contributions but also illustrate how the integrated framework facilitates new ways to manage and optimize energy distribution networks.

Additionally, throughout this process, specific links between the various project outputs were identified, highlighting the interconnections of different research areas within the InnoCyPES project. These connections reinforce the value of an integrated approach, enabling a comprehensive understanding of the complexities within energy distribution systems and offering new perspectives for future research and development in digital energy systems.

7 References

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